

Machine Learning Techniques Applied to Residential Home Price Estimations

Robust Regression and Bootstrapping for Bias and Precision Quantification

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Albert J. Lee¹, Alan Salzberg²

Abstract

Automated valuation models (AVMs) have gained popularity with the rise of online platforms like Zillow. However, the noisy nature of residential home sales data poses challenges for estimation and prediction methods that assume normality. As a result, some AVMs could exhibit significant bias and imprecision during validations. To address this issue, we employed a robust regression method (MM-estimation) combined with a bootstrapping procedure (Stine 1985) to downweigh outliers. This approach yielded unbiased and precise regression estimated residential prices, as demonstrated through k-fold validation. Additionally, this method provides a confidence interval for each residential property, enabling property-level hypothesis testing, which is uncommon for AVMs. The k-fold validation confirms that these confidence intervals exhibit the required level of statistical confidence.

Key Words: machine learning, robust regression, bootstrapping, automated valuation, validation

Background on the 2008 Subprime Financial Crisis

The 2008 subprime financial crisis was the most severe economic downturn since the Great Depression, triggered by the collapse of the U.S. housing market and the widespread failure of residential mortgage-backed securities (RMBS) tied to risky subprime loans. During the housing boom of the early 2000s, banks, mortgage lenders, and investors increasingly extended credit to borrowers with weaker credit histories, fueling demand for homes and pushing property prices to unsustainable levels. Many of these loans were bundled into RMBS and sold to investors worldwide under the assumption that credit risks—borrower’s credit worthiness and residential home values—were adequately assessed.

When housing prices began to decline in 2006, delinquencies and foreclosures spiked, leading to massive losses on these mortgage-backed securities. The fallout exposed widespread issues of loan origination fraud, inflated appraisals, poor underwriting standards, and other failures in the securitization process. Financial institutions holding large volumes of RMBS suffered catastrophic losses, contributing to the failure or bailout of major firms and a global credit freeze.

In the aftermath, the Federal Housing Finance Agency (FHFA), acting as a conservator for Fannie Mae and Freddie Mac, pursued litigation against 12 of the world’s largest investment banks, alleging that they misrepresented the quality of loans underlying the RMBS sold to the government-sponsored enterprises. These cases centered on systemic overstatements of appraisal values and

¹ Albert J. Lee, Summit, 777 6th St. NW, Suite 520, Washington, DC 20001, Albert.lee@summitllc.us

² Alan Salzberg, Salt Hill Statistical Consulting, New York, salzberg@salthillstatistics.com

misrepresentations of the underwriting standards applied to the collateral loans, which resulted in significant investor losses.³

We served as a consulting and testifying expert in some of these landmark RMBS cases brought by FHFA against the investment banks. Our expertise contributed to the analysis of appraisal practices. Using loan-level and housing market data, we assessed whether the collateral valuations were overstated relative to prevailing market values. While many cases settled prior to trial, FHFA v. Nomura proceeded to trial, making a large quantity of analyses available for public record.

Later, one of us testified at trial in *Massachusetts Mutual Life Insurance Company v. DLJ Mortgage Capital, Inc.*, another significant RMBS case addressing similar allegations of inflated collateral appraisals and misrepresentations in securitization practices.⁴ Building on the public record of the Massachusetts Mutual case, this paper focuses on an econometric model we developed to ascertain whether and to what extent appraisal values were inflated for the residential properties used to collateralize these at-issue RMBS. We developed a model that could handle notoriously noisy and heterogeneous residential housing data. To determine that individual appraisal values were inflated as compared to prevailing market values, we calculated what the market values would have been, and used confidence intervals to test relevant hypotheses. To substantiate the credibility of these estimations, we devised a series of validations showing the point estimates are unbiased, and the confidence intervals meet their purported level of confidence.

Methodological Framework

Predictive models increasingly shape decisions across industries, yet most rely on statistical assumptions that rarely hold up in practice. Non-normal residuals, heteroskedasticity, and outliers are common in real-world data, undermining model accuracy, introducing bias, and distorting measures of precision (Kennedy 2008; Gujarati 2003). These challenges appear across fields—finance, economics, real estate, health care—and demand solutions that work under messier conditions. This paper presents a generalized framework that combines robust regression and bootstrapping to address these issues (Huber 1981; Hampel et al. 1986; Stine 1985). Robust regression reduces the influence of extreme observations, producing more reliable estimates, while bootstrapping generates empirical confidence intervals that capture uncertainty without relying on parametric assumptions (Efron and Tibshirani 1993). Together, these methods produce reliable estimates that appropriately account for statistical uncertainties. To demonstrate the framework’s practical value, we apply it to residential home price estimation, a task known for its noisy, heterogeneous data (CoreLogic 2015).

A. Robust Regression

Robust regression techniques, such as MM-estimation and Huber/Bisquare weighting, address the limitations of ordinary least squares (OLS) when data contain outliers or violate normality assumptions (Huber 1981; Judge et al. 1985). Robust regression down-weights outliers “so that the regression captures the pattern in the majority of the data rather than tracks outliers” (Stine 1989). Therefore, robust regression is the preferred method for analyzing data containing outliers as it provides results resistant to the artificial impact of outliers (Alma 2011). Multiple disciplines and industries such as the materials sciences, neuroimaging, genetics, chemistry, and civil engineering frequently apply robust regression estimations (Dervilis et al. 2015; Fritsch et al. 2015; Kesselmeier et al. 2014; Li et al. 2013; Moena and Serpell 2014).

³ For example: <https://www.fhfa.gov/news/news-release/fhfa-announces-5.5-billion-settlement-with-royal-bank-of-scotland>. The 12 defendant banks include: Bank of American/Countrywide/Merrill Lynch, Royal Bank of Scotland, JPMorgan, Goldman Sachs, Deutsche Bank, Credit Suisse, UBS, Nomura, HSBC (\$550M), Barclays, Citigroup, and First Horizon.

⁴ We built on evidence made public in FHFA v. Nomura (Southern District of New York) and Massachusetts Mutual v. DLJ Mortgage Capital (Eastern District of Massachusetts).

B. Bootstrapping for Uncertainty Quantification

Our approach to calculating confidence intervals corresponds with robust regression. We did not make any parametric assumption regarding model error distribution. Instead, we used bootstrapping, which is a nonparametric approach that substitutes the actual data distribution for any assumption distributions. By resampling residuals, refitting models, and aggregating predictions, bootstrapping creates empirical distributions of model estimates. These distributions support constructing percentile-based confidence intervals, which do not depend on normality (Singh 1981). Consequently, bootstrapping provides a flexible, nonparametric way to quantify prediction uncertainty (Efron and Tibshirani 1993).

C. Combined Framework

We followed the Stine (1985) approach, integrating robust regression with bootstrapped residual distributions. This procedure generates confidence intervals for regression prediction estimates, which quantify two sources of uncertainty: sample-to-sample variability and model residuals. Appendix A contains detailed steps associated with the application bootstrapping procedure.

Regression Model Specification for House Price Estimation

Regression models have long been used to estimate prices—including residential home prices. Almost a century ago, Hass applied a regression model to estimate the value of farmland (Colwell et al. 1999). Between 1995 and 2005, Sirmans et al. (2005) identified 125 studies published that estimate house prices econometrically as a function of physical characteristics and other factors.

Multiple regression analysis is well accepted in the real estate industry by academics and practitioners alike (Appraisal Institute 2013; Betts et al. 2001; Smith et al. 1995). In many applications, a multiple regression model is a mathematical equation expressing the value of a dependent variable (e.g., the natural log of sales price) as a function of independent variables (e.g., real estate characteristics).

An appraisal expert provided the following regression specification: The dependent variable is the logarithm of sale price.⁵ Predictors include the natural log of tax assessed value (TAV), the number of days between a comparable's sale date and the subject's appraisal's date, a function of the comparable's longitude and latitude. When available, the specification also includes the year when the comparable was built, its square footage, lot size in acres, and number of bathrooms.⁶

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\text{sales price}) = & B_0 + B_1 \log(\text{TAV}) + B_2 \text{days} + B_3 \text{days}^2 + B_4 \text{lon} + B_5 \text{lat} + B_6 (\text{lon} * \text{lat}) \\ & + B_7 \text{lon}^2 + B_8 \text{lat}^2 + B_9 (\text{square feet}) \\ & + B_{10} (\text{lot acres}) + B_{11} (\text{year built}) + B_{12} (\text{bathrooms}) + \epsilon \end{aligned}$$

Variable Definitions

- **Sales price:** Sales price of comparable sale
- **TAV:** Tax assessed value of comparable sale
- **Days:** Number of days between sale date of comparable sale and the appraisal date

⁵ U.S. Government Publishing Office “Title 12, Chapter 1, Part 34, Subpart C, 34.42g,” defines market values as “the most probable price which a property should bring in a competitive and open market under all conditions requisite to a fair sale, the buyer and seller each acting prudently and knowledgeably, and assuming the price is not affected by undue stimulus.”

⁶ Dr. John Kilpatrick specified this regression equation. A review of the literature establishes that these predictors are standard among published pricing models. Sirmans et al. (2005), who surveyed 125 studies published between 1995 and 2005, concluded that the most common structural characteristics are property age or year built (used in 78 studies), square footage (used in 69 studies), lot size in acres (used in 52 studies), and number of bathrooms (used in 40 studies).

- **LON, LAT:** Longitude and latitude of comparable sale, respectively
- **YEAR BUILT:** Year built
- **Square Feet:** Square footage
- **Lot Acres:** Lot size in acres
- **Bathrooms:** Number of bathrooms
- ϵ : Error term

Data Sources

Two principal data sources are used in the model estimation: First is a sample of subject properties—residential homes for which we estimate their market value based on their property characteristics.⁷ Second is a set of comparable properties, which provides sale prices and properties characteristics. These comparable sales were selected from the general housing stock in data collected and maintained by real estate data vendors (e.g., CoreLogic or Quantarium). These data vendors maintain comprehensive databases that contain sales and tax assessor records.

We followed appraisal practices matching subject properties with their comparable properties.⁸ For example, subject and comparable properties are from the same county. Comparable sales and subject properties' appraisal dates are within 365 days of each other. Because subject properties are middle-class residential homes, we excluded comparable properties with extreme sale prices (either excessively high or low).⁹ For each subject property, we match no more than 2,000 comparable properties and no fewer than 100 comparable properties.¹⁰ In our experience, an average regression relies on data from about 1,500 comparable properties.

Estimation Techniques

While real estate property valuation can be performed with an OLS regression method, in the presence of statistical outlier, OLS may produce substantial model error and may be inferior to other non-linear methods (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).¹¹ Robust regression uses weighting to reduce the influence of a small number of unusual observations.

Specifically, we applied MM-estimates, which are a class of robust estimates for the linear model. MM-estimation refers to two stages. In the first stage, it excludes extremely large outliers. The literature calls this the S-estimation. The second stage calculates a weight for each comparable property, which is inversely proportional to the difference between the comparable property's actual sales prices and its prediction, namely, the larger the difference, the smaller the weight.

Using these weights, the second stage recalculates a new set of regression coefficients. This new set leads to new predictions and their differences with the actual sales prices among the comparable properties. This gives us a second set of weights that are likely different from the first set of weights.

⁷ Depending on applications, there are two sources of statistical uncertainty. First is the modeling error. Because the regression specification does not exhaustively include every factor that could influence market value, the model error term captures the impact of these unspecified factors. Because subject properties are sampled, if an application requires population inferences, sample-to-sample variability would be the second source of statistical uncertainty.

⁸ Dr. John Kilpatrick specified these property matching criteria.

⁹ In practice, these price boundaries are determined by 50% of the lowest subject sales price and appraisal value, and 200% of the highest subject sale price and appraisal value.

¹⁰ Consistent with appraisal practices, if more than 2,000 comparable sales meet the aforementioned criteria for a subject property, only the 2,000 geographically nearest sales are selected to be used in the estimation.

¹¹ OLS is best among the class of linear unbiased estimators. There could be superior non-linear estimators when the residuals are non-normal.

The new set of weights leads to a new set of regression coefficients with a new set of weight for the next regression, and so on. This iterative process stops when the penultimate and ultimate sets of weights are identical. The literature calls this iterative process the M-estimation.

The MM-estimation model is recognized in academic literature as among the best robust regression models. MM-estimates simultaneously have two desirable properties: (1) they are highly effective when the errors have a normal distribution; and (2) their breakdown point is 0.5 (Yohai 1987).¹² Namely, MM-estimation models perform well when there are outliers. When there are no outliers, the model performs virtually the same as OLS.

For each subject property, this process produces a distribution of estimated values (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Frequently, the median corresponds to the mode of the distribution, which is the point estimate valuation of a subject property. The 2.5th percentile and the 97.5th percentile form the lower and upper bounds of the 95-percent confidence interval.

Model Validation and Diagnostics

We evaluated model performance of the robust regression model using two approaches: cross-validation and model fit. Cross-validation uses one set of data to fit the model (training set) and a second set of data to test the model's estimates (validation set). The training and validation sets can then be reversed. In this way, the model's results can be tested against the entire data set independent of the data used to fit the model. Specifically, we validated by setting aside a validation set containing 10% of comparable sales, leaving the rest of the 90% of comparable sales to estimate the robust regression model. By rotating the validation set 10 times, we validated the robust regression estimates against all available comparable sales that were matched to the subject properties.

Based on this method, we calculated the difference between the robust regression prediction and the known sales price for the comparable sales. In general, the median difference is approximately \$100, compared to a typical residential home sale price of about \$250,000. This validation result demonstrates that the robust regression predictions are accurate at the median—the model is no more likely to under-predict sales price as it is to over-predict it (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

We also calculated the median absolute deviation to quantify model precision. Median absolute deviation (MAD) is the mid-point of the absolute difference between the robust regression estimate and the actual comparable sales price. In general, the MAD of the differences between model estimates and actual sale prices is less than 10%. This pattern shows that more than half of the robust regression estimates are within 10% of sale price. We also found that about 70% of the estimates are within 15% of their sales prices. This finding shows that the robust regression model produces precise estimates that meet appraisal industry standards.

From time to time, we may also have access to subject properties' sale price.¹³ When comparing the robust regression estimates to subject properties' sale prices, we noted that the average and median difference is about one percent.

The confidence intervals are accurate if their coverage corresponds to the stated level of confidence. For example, an accurate two-sided 95% confidence interval will include the sales price for 95% of the properties. We validate the accuracy of the confidence intervals using two sets of values: comparable sale prices and, when available, subject sale prices. These validation exercises show that the confidence intervals exhibit the requisite width, including the actual sale prices with the

¹² Specifically, we implemented the `rlm()` function in the R package MASS with MM-estimation, which defaults to the Bisquare function, a maximum of 500 iterations.

¹³ This access applies if a subject property was involved in a purchase transaction. Note that many subject properties were involved in refinance transactions for which a sale price was unavailable.

stated percentage, thus demonstrating the accuracy of the confidence intervals (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Practical Implications

This paper shows that robust regression coupling with bootstrapping is a practical approach to handling noisy and heterogenous data. In many practical settings, we want to use as much data as possible. However, due to the data size, curating a dataset free of outliers is not always practical. The cases we worked on were large and often involved thousands of subject properties, requiring tens of millions of comparable properties for the regressions. Although it is easy to spot univariate outliers by examining summary statistics, multivariate structural outliers are far harder to identify. Robust regression uses a weighting mechanism that assigns a lower weight for any outliers. This weighting is a significant advantage in a production environment where many estimations are automated.

As far as we could tell, most commercially available models estimating residential home prices do not provide or disclose a confidence interval along with a point estimate. The methodology described here incorporates confidence interval production as part of the estimation. These confidence intervals are integral to any hypothesis testing; without them it would be hard to judge the reliability of a residential home price estimate.

Exhibits

Figure 1: A simulated quantile-quantile (QQ) plot

Figure 2: A simulated price distribution for a hypothetical property

Figure 3: A simulated error distribution

Simulated 95% Confidence Intervals for Home Price Estimates
(Coverage: 96.0%)

Figure 4: A simulated set of confidence intervals

Appendix A: Bootstrapping Steps

Bootstrapping Steps for Estimating Confidence Intervals in Property Valuation

1. Estimate Initial Robust Regression
 - Use robust regression (e.g., MM-estimator via `rlm()` in R) to fit a model for each subject property using its set of comparable sales.
 - Record the regression residuals from this model.
2. Bootstrap Comparable Residuals
 - Randomly sample (with replacement) residuals from the comparable sales residuals to generate bootstrap datasets.
 - This preserves the structure of the predictors but varies the outcome to simulate alternate realities.
3. Generate Bootstrapped Comparable Sale Prices
 - For each bootstrap sample, add the bootstrapped residuals back to the predicted values (from the original robust regression).
 - This creates a new pseudo-sample of sale prices consistent with the underlying model.
4. Reestimate Robust Regression
 - Fit a new robust regression model on each bootstrapped pseudo-sample.
 - Apply the new regression to the subject property's characteristics to generate a predicted value.
5. Repeat the Bootstrapping Process
 - Repeat steps 2–4 1,001 times to generate a distribution of subject property predictions.
6. Construct Confidence Interval
 - Take the median of the 1,001 predicted values as the point estimate.
 - The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrapped predictions form the 95% confidence interval.
 - This captures the uncertainty in the valuation due to sampling variability in the comparable sales.

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